

**Tailoring composition and nanostructures in supramolecular solvents: Impact on
the extraction efficiency of polyphenols from vegetal biomass**

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

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Table S1. Adducts of octanol and 1,2-octanediol monitored in LC-(APCI)HR-MS (molecular formula, precursor ion m/z and ionization mode).

Compound adduct	Molecular formula	Precursor ion (m/z)	Ionization mode
1-Octanol+ACN	C ₁₀ H ₂₅ ON ₂	172.1696	Positive
1,2-Octanediol +ACN-OH	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ ON	170.1539	Positive

Table S2. Percentage of amphiphile incorporated into the SUPRAS phase with respect to that amount of amphiphile employed for the synthesis (average of three replicates).

Synthesis conditions		1-Octanol incorporated into SUPRAS (%)	1,2-Octanediol incorporated into SUPRAS (%)
THF % (V/V)			
5		97.96	94.26
15		-	94.49
30		99.11	-
70		100.10	-
Ethanol % (V/V)			
5		100.40	94.22
15		100.38	94.27
50		98.55	-
1-propanol % (V/V)			
5		100.21	95.59
15		100.09	96.76
50		100.09	
1,3-propanediol % (V/V)			
15		-	88.51
30		-	93.20

Table S3. Equations to predict the generated volume of 1-octanol-based SUPRAS as a function of the percentages of amphiphile and of organic solvent employed for their synthesis.

1-octanol-THF-SUPRAS					
^a 1-Octanol (%, w/v)	Equation	R ²	^b THF (%, v/v)	Equation	R ²
2.5	$y = 28.83e^{0.039z}$	0.9833	5	$y = 12.371x - 0.6455$	0.9984
5	$y = 48.494e^{0.0393z}$	0.9886	10	$y = 15.675x - 11.303$	0.9742
8	$y = 85.89e^{0.0324z}$	0.9949	15	$y = 15.134x + 13.449$	0.9924
10	$y = 106.2e^{0.0298z}$	0.9968	20	$y = 17.658x + 9.8028$	0.9919
15	$y = 171.01e^{0.0223z}$	0.9973	30	$y = 20.793x + 43.205$	0.9664
			40	$y = 22.991x + 108.68$	0.9403
			50	$y = 18.238x + 268.61$	0.953

1-octanol-ethanol-SUPRAS					
^a 1-Octanol (%, w/v)	Equation	R ²	^b Ethanol (%, v/v)	Equation	R ²
5	$y = 60.572e^{0.0156z}$	0.9624	5	$y = 12.284x + 4.6414$	0.9979
8	$y = 83.072e^{0.0181z}$	0.9021	10	$y = 13.953x - 7.3344$	0.9952
10	$y = 114.41e^{0.0152z}$	0.9567	15	$y = 13.041x + 9.0966$	0.9716
15	$y = 143.92e^{0.0222z}$	0.9106	20	$y = 13.821x + 6.4048$	0.9886
			30	$y = 16.065x + 5.3081$	0.9869
			40	$y = 22.817x - 7.9772$	0.9913

1-octanol-1-propanol- SUPRAS					
^a 1-Octanol (%, w/v)	Equation	R ²	^b 1-propanol (%, v/v)	Equation	R ²
5	$y = 51.815e^{0.049z}$	0.9935	5	$y = 12.668x + 5.9215$	0.9837
8	$y = 87.772e^{0.0391z}$	0.9885	10	$y = 12.986x + 26.196$	0.9828
10	$y = 102.77e^{0.0371z}$	0.9938	15	$y = 16.05x + 18.078$	0.9889
15	$y = 168.14e^{0.0278z}$	0.9979	20	$y = 15.768x + 51.674$	0.9976
			30	$y = 18.775x + 109.6$	0.9326
			40	$y = 13.035x + 327.85$	0.9359

^a Equations derived from a fixed concentration of 1-octanol and variable percentages of organic solvent;

^b Equations derived from a fixed concentration of organic solvent and variable percentages of 1-octanol;

z: % v/v organic solvent; x: % w/v amphiphile, y: volume of SUPRAS

Table S4. Equations to predict the generated volume of 1,2-Octanediol-based SUPRAS as a function of the percentages of amphiphile and of organic solvent employed for their synthesis.

1,2-octanediol-THF- SUPRAS					
^a 1,2-Octanediol (%, w/v)	Equation	R ²	^b THF (%, v/v)	Equation	R ²
8%	$y = 117.1e^{0.0285z}$	0.9943	5%	$y = 19.893x - 24.711$	0.9992
10%	$y = 144.25e^{0.0353z}$	0.9783	10%	$y = 19.535x - 1.8023$	0.9978
15%	$y = 231.16e^{0.0261z}$	0.9606	15%	$y = 22.696x + 1.819$	0.9978

1,2-octanediol-ethanol- SUPRAS					
^a 1,2-Octanediol (%, w/v)	Equation	R ²	^b Ethanol (%, v/v)	Equation	R ²
8%	$y = 101.47e^{0.029z}$	0.9911	5%	$y = 17.909x - 9.8515$	0.9994
10%	$y = 144.62e^{0.0238z}$	0.9531	10%	$y = 18.561x - 8.0819$	0.9994
15%	$y = 225.03e^{0.0216z}$	0.9314	15%	$y = 21.112x - 14.418$	0.9992
			20%	$y = 25.68x - 23.502$	0.9987

1,2-octanediol-1-propanol- SUPRAS					
^a 1,2-Octanediol (%, w/v)	Equation	R ²	^b 1-propanol (%, v/v)	Equation	R ²
8%	$y = 112.43e^{0.044z}$	0.9888	5%	$y = 20.192x - 19.843$	0.9972
10%	$y = 143.87e^{0.0399z}$	0.9557	10%	$y = 20.3x + 1.5058$	0.999
15%	$y = 229.24e^{0.0319z}$	0.9491	15%	$y = 23.835x + 8.0165$	0.9829
			20%	$y = 25.234x + 76.191$	0.998

1,2-octanediol-1,3-propanediol- SUPRAS					
^a 1,2-Octanediol (%, w/v)	Equation	R ²	^b 1,3- propanediol (%, v/v)	Equation	R ²
8%	$y = 121.79e^{0.0077z}$	0.9972	15 %	$y = 20.215x - 34.903$	0.9853
10%	$y = 148.06e^{0.0104z}$	0.9975	20 %	$y = 21.268x - 36.493$	0.9852
15%	$y = 204.99e^{0.0149z}$	0.9905	30 %	$y = 24.278x - 40.959$	0.9994

^a Equations derived from a fixed concentration of 1,2-octanediol and variable percentages of organic solvent; ^bEquations derived from a fixed concentration of organic solvent and variable percentages of 1,2-octanediol; z: % v/v organic solvent; x: % w/v amphiphile, y: volume of SUPRAS

Table S5. Identified phenolic compounds in SUPRAS extracts (molecular formula, precursor and product ions m/z and ionization mode)

Compound	Formula	Precursor ion (m/z)	Product ions (m/z)		Ionization mode
Quercetin	C15H10O7	303.0427	280.401	257.0450	Positive
Quercetin-arabinoside	C20H18O11	435.0849	303.0608	-	Positive
Quercetin-hexoside	C21H20O12	464.0955	303.0608	-	Positive
Quercetin-rhamnetihexoside	C27H30O16	611.1616	465.1183	303.0608	Positive
Kaempferol	C15H10O6	287.0477	269.227	137.0232	Positive
Kaempferol-hexoside	C21H20O11	449.1006	287.0557	-	Positive
Kaempferol-dihexoside	C27H30O16	611.1534	287.0656	449.1230	Positive
Coumaric acid	C9H8O3	164.0401	119.0000	117.1000	Negative
Coumaric acid hexoside	C15H18O8	327.1002	295.0607	165.0547	Positive
Catechin	C15H14O6	291.0790	273.0765	139.0388	Positive
Catechin-hexoside	C21H24O11	451.1245	393.1542	350.9861	Negative
Catechin-dihexoside	C27H34O16	614,1847	273.0894	-	Positive
Chlorogenic acid	C16H18O9	353.0961	191.0611	-	Negative
Naringenin hexoside	C21H22O10	434.1213	273.0971	-	Positive
Procyanidin dimer	C30H26O12	578.1424	291.0870	427.1169	Positive

Figure S1. Measured volumes of 1-octanol-based SUPRAS prepared using different organic solvents and as a function of the initial concentration of organic solvent (A, C, E, G) or of the initial concentration of amphiphile (B, D, F, H). Relative standard deviations of volume measurements in the range 1-5 %.

Figure S2. Measured volumes of 1,2-octanediol-based SUPRAS prepared using different organic solvents and as a function of the initial concentration of organic solvent (A, C, E, G) or of the initial concentration of amphiphile (B, D, F, H). Relative standard deviations of volume measurements in the range 1-5 %.

Figure S3. Agreement between the measured volumes of SUPRAS and those calculated using the proposed equations (A) SUPRAS of 1-octanol:THF:water (B) SUPRAS of 1-octanol:ethanol:water (C) SUPRAS of 1-octanol:1-propanol:water (D) SUPRAS of 1,2-octanediol:THF:water (E) SUPRAS of 1,2-octanediol:ethanol:water (F) SUPRAS of 1,2-octanediol:1-propanol:water (G) SUPRAS of 1,2-octanediol:1,3-propanediol:water.

D

Octanediol-THF

E

Octanediol-EtOH

F

Octanediol-Propanol

Figure S4. Micrographs obtained by (A) light microscopy in the bright field (A) and cryo- SEM (B) for alkanol-based SUPRAS, along with (C) a schematic of the nanostructure.

Figure S5. Extraction of catechin and coumaric acid their glycosides from raspberries employing different SUPRAS. (A) 1-octanol, ethanol; (B) 1-octanol, 1-propanol; (C) 1-octanol, THF; (D) 1,2-octanediol, 1,3-propanediol; (E) 1,2-octanediol, ethanol; (F) 1,2-octanediol, 1-propanol; (G) 1,2-octanediol, THF.

